

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Dec. temp. °C	Conduc-tance* $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.) N	Halogen
1.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{Br}^-$	Yellow	215-216	29.8	3.32 (3.48)	19.93 (19.89)
2.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{I}^-$	Yellow	185-187	28.6	3.10 (3.12)	28.22 (28.28)
3.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{CuCl}_2^-$	Green	98-100	30.2	2.80 (2.85)	21.61 (21.65)
4.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{ZnCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$	Greenish yellow	210-212	30.4	2.56 (2.74)	20.64 (20.81)
5.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]_2\text{CdCl}_2^-$	Yellow	278-280	50.2	2.60 (2.77)	14.20 (14.05)
6.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{HgCl}_2^-$	Yellow	140-142	30.0	2.08 (2.23)	16.80 (16.93)
7.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{Br}^-$	Green	280-282	28.8	3.01 (3.15)	17.82 (17.95)
8.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{I}^-$	Green	216-218	28.6	2.68 (2.84)	25.82 (25.79)
9.	$\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})^+\text{CuCl}_2^-$	Yellowish green	158-160	30.2	2.50 (2.62)	19.86 (19.90)
10.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{ZnCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$	Green	218-220	31.2	2.41 (2.53)	19.12 (19.25)
11.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})]_2\text{CdCl}_2^-$	Yellowish green	146-150	50.6	2.49 (2.66)	13.32 (13.47)
12.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{HgCl}_2^-$	Yellowish green	176-178	28.8	2.01 (2.08)	15.71 (15.84)

* $0.50 \times 10^4 M$

disappearance of the broad $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ at $3\ 600\text{--}3\ 560\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ and appearance of a medium intensity band at $520\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ show the deprotonation of phenolic OH group and bonding of the 8-hydroxy-quinoline ligand to the metal through phenolic oxygen⁶.

The bands occurring consistently around $3\ 080$ (C—H stretch), $1\ 430$ (asymmetric ring breathing), $1\ 080$ (C—H deformation of C_8H_8 ring) and $815\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (C—H bending out-of-plane deformation) in all the complexes suggest the presence of η^5 -cyclopentadienyl ring⁶. An additional band near $440\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\text{M-C}_8\text{H}_8$ vibrations⁷.

Pmr spectra : ^1H nmr spectra of the complexes were recorded in deuterated acetone. The spectra of free oxine show the signals at $\delta\ 7.31$ (4H, m), 8.05 (1H, q, $J\ 9.0$ and 2.5 Hz) and 8.73 (1H, q, $J\ 4.0$ and 1.6 Hz) due to the $\text{C}_{8,6,6,7}$, C_4 and C_2 protons, respectively. In the metal complexes, however, the former two signals (due to the $\text{C}_{8,6,6,7}$ and C_4) are not separately identifiable and resulting in a complex multiplet in the region $\delta\ 7.4\text{--}8.2$. The resonance due to the C_2 protons is at $\delta\ 9.06$ (q, $J\ 4.0$ and 1.8 Hz). The fact that it is shifted downfield with respect to the free oxine, supports the conclusion that the oxinate ligand is chelating. The spectra of the $\text{ZnCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$ salts show an additional resonance signal due to the presence of a coordinated water molecules at $\delta\ 4.18$. The resonance signals due to C_8H_8 group is observed as a singlet at $\delta\ 6.7$.

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Five- and Six-coordinate Low-spin Iron(III) Complexes

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IRON(III) is known to form high-spin, ($S=5/2$) low-spin ($S=1/2$) and intermediate-spin ($S=3/2$) complexes under the influence of different ligand fields. Spin-crossover phenomenon is usually observed with the iron(III) compounds. Examples of high-spin and spin-crossover compounds of iron(III) are numerous. However, there exists limited examples of low-spin iron(III) complexes. In continuation to our studies on iron(III)¹, we report in

the present communication, some simple anionic iron(III) complexes which are found to have low-spin states.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Suspension of tetramethylammoniumtetrachloroferrate(III) in ethanol was reacted with 2-benzazine/3 5-dimethylpyridine/3-methylpyridine / 1,3-diazole/2-methyl-1,3-benzodiazole / 4,5-diazaphenanthrene/1,2-diaminoethane in appropriate molar ratio, refluxed for a few minutes and cooled. The separated compounds were filtered through a sintered glass crucible, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous calcium chloride.

The composition of the complexes was established through elemental analyses carried out by standard methods. The conductance measurements in methanol medium were carried out using a Systronics 303 direct reading conductivity meter. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature with a Gouy balance and calculation was made computing diamagnetic corrections from Pascal's constant². The ir spectra of the compounds were recorded in the region 4 000-400 cm^{-1} using a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer with KBr optics. The electronic spectra of the solution in methanol medium were obtained using a Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer. The molecular weight of the complexes was determined by Rast's method using diphenyl and C, H analyses were done by a Systems Control Semiautomatic instrument. The analytical data are returned in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The compounds reported in the present communication belong to five- and six-coordinated cate-

gories. The coordination number and probable stereochemistry of these compounds have been suggested on the basis of their analytical data, infrared and electronic spectra, electrical conductivity, room temperature magnetic susceptibility and molecular weight determination. The values of Δ_m obtained between 112 and 169 Ω^{-1} (Table 1) in methanol medium indicate that the compounds are 1:1 electrolytes³. The low-spin compounds give rise to the $^6T_{2g}$ term, and the temperature-dependent magnetic moment is a function of spin-coupling parameter. The magnetic moment value is expected to be above spin-only value (1.73 B.M) and less than about 2.5 B.M⁴. The observed values range 1.34-2.21 B.M. for hexacoordinated and 2.43-2.98 B.M. for pentacoordinated complexes. The μ_{eff} values for the latter are intermediate between spin-free and spin-paired complexes and can be attributed due to the spin-crossover system⁵⁻⁷. The molecular weight determination indicates that the complexes are monomeric.

Infrared spectra : The relevant infrared absorption bands due to the coordinated chelate of the complexes are discussed below. Bands due to tetramethylammonium ion⁸ were obtained at 700-800 and 935-980 cm^{-1} . The ν_{C-H} band observed at $\sim 3\ 000\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu_{C-C} + \nu_{C-N}$ bands at $\sim 1\ 600$ and $1\ 560\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ indicate the coordination of the substituted pyridine^{9,10}. In the spectra of the 1,3-diazole complexes, the N-H bending and stretching frequencies which occur at $\sim 1\ 465$ and $\sim 3\ 300\ \text{cm}^{-1}$, respectively, clearly indicate that 1,3-diazole and its derivative are coordinated through the tertiary nitrogen atom as confirmed by the reported X-ray structural studies¹¹. 1,2-Diaminoethane shows two bands at 1 700-1 500 and 950-850 cm^{-1} due to NH_2 stretching and CH_2 rocking¹². In the present investigation, the former band is observed at 1 580 cm^{-1} whereas the latter is overlapped with the

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF SOME ANIONIC IRON(III) COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Δ_m $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ mol ⁻¹	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)				μ_{eff} B.M.	Mol wt* Found/(Calcd.)
					Fe	Cl	C	H		
1.	[C ₄ H ₁₁ N][FeCl ₄ (β -pic)]	Yellow	252	142.6	15.30 (14.60)	38.8 (37.2)	32.8 (32.9)	5.1 (5.2)	2.46	320.4 (364.98)
2.	[C ₄ H ₁₁ N][FeCl ₄ (β -pic) ₂]	Dark yellow	246	169.0	12.1 (13.1)	31.0 (33.3)	40.3 (41.9)	5.6 (5.7)	2.21	430.2 (458.11)
3.	[C ₄ H ₁₁ N][FeCl ₄ (iq)]	Yellow	249	159.6	13.9 (14.0)	35.4 (34.9)	38.3 (38.9)	1.7 (4.7)	2.98	376.4 (401.01)
4.	[C ₄ H ₁₁ N][FeCl ₄ (iq) ₂]	Dark yellow	235	112.2	10.5 (10.9)	26.7 (27.2)	48.9 (49.8)	4.3 (4.9)	2.05	502.6 (530.17)
5.	[C ₄ H ₁₁ N][FeCl ₄ (lu)]	Reddish yellow	223	139.2	14.7 (13.9)	37.4 (37.1)	35.0 (34.8)	4.9 (5.5)	2.43	330.4 (378.85)
6.	[C ₄ H ₁₁ N][FeCl ₄ (lu) ₂]	Reddish yellow	195	145.8	11.4 (11.3)	29.2 (30.2)	44.5 (44.5)	6.0 (6.2)	1.94	445.8 (485.85)
7.	[C ₄ H ₁₁ N][FeCl ₄ (iz)]	Orange	248	120.2	16.4 (16.5)	41.7 (40.3)	24.6 (24.7)	4.3 (4.7)	2.4 ⁹	300.1 (339.85)
8.	[C ₄ H ₁₁ N][FeCl ₄ (me biz)]	Orange	255	126.3	13.8 (14.1)	35.1 (34.9)	35.3 (35.6)	4.8 (4.9)	2.57	400.8 (403.85)
9.	[C ₄ H ₁₁ N][FeCl ₄ (en)]	Yellow	203	120.5	15.8 (15.8)	40.3 (40.1)	20.9 (21.6)	5.9 (6.0)	2.12	307.6 (331.85)
10.	[C ₄ H ₁₁ N][FeCl ₄ (<i>o</i> -phen)]	Dark	252	118.5	15.3 (12.1)	31.4 (29.8)	40.6 (42.5)	4.1 (4.4)	1.99	410.5 (451.85)

*Values calculated for 1 : 1 electrolytic complexes.

band of $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ ion at 935 cm^{-1} . The $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ at 1580 cm^{-1} and $\delta_{\text{C-H}}$ at 760 cm^{-1} indicate the bidentate nature of 4,5-diazaphenanthrene coordinating through both the nitrogen atoms¹⁸⁻¹⁶. The absence of band at $3200\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes attributable to coordinated water molecules indicate that water is not coordinated to the metal ion even in the pentacoordinated species¹⁶.

In the electronic spectra of the octahedral complexes, bands were obtained at ~ 660 , ~ 550 and $\sim 412\text{ nm}$, which may be assigned to ${}^3\text{T}_2 \rightarrow {}^3\text{E}_1$, ${}^3\text{T}_2 \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_1$ and ${}^3\text{T}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1$ transitions. The values are consistent with the earlier observations¹⁷.

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Studies on Water Decomposition Product of Iron(III) Peroxychromate by Ion-exchange Resins

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Several peroxychromates have earlier been reported¹⁻⁵ but not iron peroxychromate. Hence, to ascertain the composition of iron(III) peroxychromate the study of its water decomposition product has been undertaken.

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Experimental

Ice-cold solid Fe^{+++} chromate⁴ (1 g) and anhydrous H_2O_2 (2.5%, 20 ml) extracted in ethyl acetate, were mixed together, shaken occasionally and cooled in a freezing mixture for 30 min. Bluish violet iron(III) peroxychromate, soluble in ethyl acetate, was separated as in other cases¹⁻⁵. The oxidising power of the peroxychromate was determined by Na_2AsO_3 and KMnO_4 methods^{1,8} (Table 1).

Many sets of water decomposition product were prepared by decomposing the peroxychromate (20 ml) in contact with water (50 ml). The colourless organic layer was removed and the yellow aqueous layer was exchanged⁶⁻⁸ with Dowex-50 (Na) and Amberlite-120 (Na) resins.

The presence of Fe^{+++} in elutriant and of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ in effluent was established by usual qualitative tests, R_f values⁹ (elutriant, 0.720; effluent, 0.319; FeCl_3 , 0.725; $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, 0.312), absorption (aqueous) and ir (KBr) spectra (effluent and $\text{Na}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$: λ_{max} at 233, 315 and 350 nm; sharp absorptions at 950, 890 and 770 cm^{-1}). The concentration of Fe^{+++} and Cr^{VI} in elutriant and effluent was estimated by colorimetric¹⁰ and gravimetric¹¹ methods (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

Average amount (g) of			Ratio		
Fe^{+++}	Cr^{VI}	Peroxy O_7^{2-}	a :	b :	c
0.00112	0.00315	0.00156	1 :	2.81 :	1.39
Calcd. :					
+ H_2O					
$\text{Fe}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3 \xrightarrow{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$			$\text{Fe}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3 + 9\text{O}$		
μ_{eff} at 304 K of elutriant - oxinate = 5.936 B.M.			1 : 2.79 : 1.28		

The changes in pH (4.75-4.85) of a set of water decomposition product, on dilution with measured volumes (25-300 ml) of water, were found almost similar to dichromate solutions⁶⁻⁷.

Results and Discussion

The above findings confirm that the water decomposition product of iron(III) peroxychromate is composed of Fe^{+++} and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ in the ratio of 1 : 3. Further, the average amounts of the constituents (Table 1) indicate that a very low percentage of iron(III) chromate is converted to peroxy compound. However, the experimental results and inferences are in agreement with the formulation^{1-5,6-7} of iron(III) peroxychromate as $\text{Fe}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$.

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